

Mixed metal complex formation of diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid involving cadmium(II) and alkaline earth metal ions

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Equilibrium studies on binary complexes of diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid with Be^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II}, Ba^{II}, Cd^{II} metal ions and its heterobinuclear ternary complexes involving Cd^{II}-Be^{II}, Cd^{II}-Mg^{II}, Cd^{II}-Ca^{II}, Cd^{II}-Sr^{II} and Cd^{II}-Ba^{II} have been carried out potentiometrically in the biologically relevant conditions. The observed order of stability constants and percent distribution of different complex species with respect to pH have been discussed. The calculations have been made using the SCOGS computer programme.

The present communication describes the formation of binary and heterobimetallic ternary complexes of DTPA. There has been an upsurge of interest in the solution chemistry of ternary complexes which are likely to be important as components of multimetal-multiligand systems in biological fluids and also as models for metalloenzyme substrate complexes¹. Some of the DTPA complexes have been utilized as contrast enhancing agents in biomedical magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)². The DTPA has been also used in decarporating some of the toxic metal ions from the body of exposed animals^{3,4}. This is the reason why the complexes of this ligand have recently become the subject of extensive investigations in solution^{5,6} and in the solid state⁷. In continuation to our earlier work^{8,9}, we report here the complex formation of the title ligand diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid with Cd^{II}-Be^{II}, Cd^{II}-Mg^{II}, Cd^{II}-Ca^{II}, Cd^{II}-Sr^{II} and Cd^{II}-Ba^{II} metals in aqueous solution. In heterobimetallic ternary complexes the alkaline earth metal ions have been taken as secondary metal ions as some of them play vital role in biological systems¹⁰.

Results and discussion

The ligand diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid titrates as a pentaprotic acid (H₅L). Its evaluated pK^H values 1.86, 2.79, 4.29, 8.02 and 10.49 correspond to successive deprotonation of the five COOH groups. This octadentate ligand forms binary complexes with Be, Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba, Cd metal ions in aqueous solution. Among these complexes, CdDTPA has the highest stability and therefore it can be presumed that in a 1 : 1, M : CdDTPA reaction mixture Cd^{II} remains fully complexed and the reaction mixture mainly contains the species [CdDTPA] and [M] at pH lower than 2.5 when pH of the reaction mixture is raised by adding alkali the dissociable protons (H⁺) of the uncoordinated

carboxyl groups of CdDTPA are displaced as per following equilibria :

The completely deprotonated ligand which becomes available in greater quantity with rising pH interacts with the other metal ions (M) forming the heterobimetallic complexes [CdMDTPA] as :

where M²⁺ = Be, Mg, Ca, Sr and Ba.

The CdDTPA complex is expected to involve four coordinate tetrahedral arrangement around Cd^{II} as this is the most preferred coordination for Cd^{II} metal ion¹¹.

With the aid of SCOGS computer programme¹², the heterobimetallic complex formation in a system of two metal ions such as Cd^{II} and M^{II} (where M^{II} = Be^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II}, Ba^{II}) with the ligand L (DTPA) in aqueous solution may be described according to the equilibrium :

where the stoichiometric number p, q, r and s are either zero or positive integers, t is a negative integer for a protonated species, positive integer for a hydroxo or a deprotonated species and zero for a neutral species.

The overall stability constant (b_{pqrst}) of the complex M¹_p M²_q L¹_r L²_s (OH)_t is defined as :

$$\beta_{pqrst} = \frac{[M^1_p M^2_q L^1_r L^2_s (OH)_t]}{[M^I]^p [M^2]^q [L^1]^r [L^2]^s [OH]^t} \quad (6)$$

Table 1. Proton-ligand and metal-ligand binary and ternary constants ($\log \beta$) at $35 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ in aqueous solution, ionic strength $I = 0.1$ (M) NaNO_3

(a) Proton-ligand constants						
Ligand	pK_5^H	pK_4^H	pK_3^H	pK_2^H	pK_1^H	
Diethylene triamine-pentaacetic acid (DTPA)	1.86	2.79	4.29	8.02	10.49	
(b) Hydrolytic constants of M^{2+} (aq.) ions						
	Cd	Be	Mg	Ca	Sr	Ba
$\log K_M^H$	-10.20	-5.70	-11.50	-11.70	-	-
$\log K_M^{2H}$	-9.08	-5.50	-	-	-	-
(c) Stability constants of binary complexes of ligand DTPA						
	Cd	Be	Mg	Ca	Sr	Ba
$\log K_{ML}^M$	19.88	-	9.40	10.80	9.80	8.62
(d) Stability constants of ternary complexes of ligand DTPA						
	Be	Mg	Ca	Sr	Ba	
$\log \beta_{CdML}^M$	21.18	20.88	21.02	20.72	20.42	

Standard deviation in the values $\pm (0.1, 0.2)$ in log units.

this equation may be used to calculate the speciation curves that provide clues to the formation equilibria of the complexes at different pH.

In the present study from the computer analysis of the pH titration data the complex species CdL , CdBeL , CdMgL , CdCaL , CdSrL , CdBaL in the CdMDTPA ($M = \text{Be, Mg, Ca, Sr and Ba}$) system have been detected in addition to protonated ligand species. The $\log \beta$ values for the mentioned species are given in Table 1. The $\log \beta$ values for binary proton ligand and metal ligand species obtained are in good agreement with the reported values given in the literature¹³. The stability of mixed-metal complexes follow the order $\text{Cd-Be} > \text{Cd-Ca} > \text{Cd-Mg} > \text{Cd-Sr} > \text{Cd-Ba}$. In general the calcium chelates have been reported to be more stable than magnesium¹⁴. Be^{II} ion being the smallest in size has the highest value of stability constant in the ternary systems.

The speciation curves indicate the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 heterobimetallic ternary complexes in the pH range 2.0 to 4.5 according to equilibria 1 to 4. The distribution of various binary and heterobimetallic ternary species for the magnesium system have been shown in Fig. 1 and in all cases concentration of heterobimetallic complex species [CdMDTPA] are higher as compared to the binary species. The concentration of the binary species never exceed 45% of the total ligand present, while the heterobimetallic ternary species has been found to be present to the extent of

more than 80%. These plots also indicate that formation of the heterobimetallic complexes starts from very low pH values and concentration increases with increase of pH values.

Fig. 1. Species distribution curve of Cd-Mg-DTPA system : where (1) H_3L , (2) H_2L , (3) FM_1 , (4) FM_2 , (5) Cd DTPA, (6) Cd Mg DTPA.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of reagent grade and their solutions were prepared in double-distilled CO₂ free water. Metal nitrate solutions were standardized by complexometric EDTA titration methods¹⁵. The ligand DTPA dissolved consuming two moles of alkali solution.

pH measurements were made with a century model CP 901-S pH-meter using a special glass electrode (accuracy ± 0.01 pH) at $35 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$.

Metal-ligand mixtures in aqueous solution were prepared for the pH-metric titrations keeping the concentrations of the common ingredients identical in all the cases, the ratio of Cd : DTPA : M² (M² = Be, Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba) 1 : 1 : 1 and the total volume 50.0 ml at a fixed ionic strength, $I = 0.1$ M (NaNO₃). All the mixtures were titrated with carbonate free 0.1 M NaOH solution. Procedure for pH-titrations was the same as described elsewhere. Ionic product of water (K_w) and activity coefficient of hydrogen ion under the experimental conditions were obtained from literature^{16,17}.

Proton-ligand and metal-ligand constants were calculated with the aid of SCOGS computer programme¹² by VINTRON computer set. Computer refined values of the constants corresponding to minimum standard deviation in the titer were used to calculate the concentration of various complex species.

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